

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B362
 Date: 06 May 2008
 Take Off: 09:10:22Z
 Landing: 13:50:46Z
 Flight Time 4h 40

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: South Germany to North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester	y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	n
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	n
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM	y
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Only PSAP
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester	n
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dan Tong	University of Manchester	n
12	PAN / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds	N,y
13	Mission Scientist 2	Megan Northway	University of Reading	y

Flight Track:

B362 Track 06-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B362
 Date: 06 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: South and West Germany to North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
071810		Start-Up	1.6 kft	000	48'05.11N, 11'17.65E
091022		T/O	3.9 kft	000	Oberpfaffenhofen
091800	092046	Profile 1	6.8 - 4.8 kft	000	7k-5.1k', QNH 1024hPa
091853		Video	6.1 kft	000	Start FFC & UFC
092047	092142	Run 1	4.8 kft	000	
092152	092203	Profile 2	4.7 - 4.6 kft	000	5.1k-4.8k'
092253	094404	Run 1	4.5 - 3.7 kft	000	
092444		Event	4.5 kft	000	Zero JW & Nevz
093645		Event	4.5 kft	000	A8
094330		Event	3.7 kft	000	Slow descent
094458		Event	3.2 kft	000	A7
094554	100446	Run 2	2.4 kft	000	2.7k'
095819		Event	2.4 kft	000	E6
100447	100554	Profile 3	2.4 - 3.4 kft	000	2.7k'-3.6k'
100555	100644	Run 3	3.4 kft	000	3.6k'
100644	100741	Profile 4	3.4 kft	000	Very busy on ATC!
100739		Event	3.4 kft	000	change level
100833	103623	Run 3	2.9 kft	000	Resume R3
101740		Event	2.9 kft	000	E5
102053		Event	2.8 kft	000	QNH 1027, adjust height
102634		Event	2.9 kft	000	Abeam E4
102816		Event	2.9 kft	000	Heimann cal
103644	103831	Run 3	2.9 kft	000	3.2k'
103832	104038	Profile 5	2.9 - 1.9 kft	000	3.2k'- to 2.3k'
104125	105726	Run 4	2.0 - 1.9 kft	000	E1
104845		Event	1.9 kft	000	E2
105019		Video	2.0 kft	000	Change tapes
105752	114555	Run 4	1.9 - 2.0 kft	000	1.5K'
110549		Event	1.9 kft	000	D1
111713		Event	1.9 kft	000	J2
114556	114731	Profile 6	2.0 - 1.2 kft	000	1.5k'
114732	115109	Run 5	1.2 kft	000	1.5k' , QNH 1029
115248	115515	Profile 7	1.2 - -.34 kft	000	1.5k'-50'
115515	120659	Profile 8	-.34 - 10.0 kft	000	A-B, from 50', QNH 1028
121113	122228	Run 6	10.0 kft	000	B-A
122237	122407	Orbit 1	10.1 - 10.0 kft	000	45deg right, st030
122439	122609	Orbit 2	10.0 - 10.1 kft	000	45deg right, st090
122729	122949	Profile 9	10.0 - 8.0 kft	000	1000fpm
123135	123552	Profile 9	8.1 - 2.2 kft	000	-2.5 k', to B
123552	124859	Run 7	2.2 - 2.1 kft	000	2.5k'
124926	125121	Profile 10	2.1 - 0.64 kft	000	2.5k'-1k'
125310	125648	Profile 10	0.62 - -.29 kft	000	1k'-50'
125659	130924	Run 8	-.23 kft	000	100', A-B
131009	131122	Orbit 3	0.16 - 0.19 kft	000	45deg right, st 040, 500'
131152	131307	Orbit 4	0.15 - 0.17 kft	000	45deg right, st 100, 500'
135046		Land	-.32 kft	000	Rotterdam
135225		ASP	-.32 kft	000	Close
135525		Shutdown	-.31 kft	000	51'56.98 N, 4'26.15E

B362 Track 06-MAY-08

**EUCAARI Flight B362 (dual flight with B363)
FAAM sortie brief**

Tuesday 6 May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight)
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight)
3. CCM (Directflight)
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics – (FAAM)
7. SWS – Debbie O’Sullivan (MO)
8. CPI rack – Dantong Liu (Manchester)
9. wet nephelometer/filters – James Bowles (MO)
10. AMS Rack – Paul Williams (Manchester)
11. CCN – Jamie Trembath (FAAM)
12. Mission Scientist – Hugh Coe (Manchester)
13. Mission Scientist 2 – Megan Northway (Reading)

Operating Area: D (UK); follow low level route #11 from Oberpfaffenhofen (OB) north to Cabauw and then work along route #1 west into UK airspace conducting radiation work. Landing at Rotterdam.

Sortie Objectives: To map out pollution outflow from Central Europe towards the UK and North Sea area and investigate the radiative properties of aerosol particles over the southern North Sea.

Weather. Atlantic low positioned west of Iceland (978 mbar) and High over Denmark, extending North-South from Norway and into Germany. A cold front associated with the low will extend N-S across the Irish Sea to Biscay, held stationary by high. Anticyclonic flow from Central Europe expected to enter southern North Sea during the day.

Define waypoints A and B 15 minutes (100 km) apart in Southern North Sea based on local conditions.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off OB at 09z (11 am local)
3. Profile from 5000’ to 2000’ and follow route #11 from OB north to Cabauw and then to UK FIR boundary (SOMVA).
[2 hr 40 min]
4. Continue at 2000’, descend to arrive Waypoint 40 (Weybourne) at 50 ft.
[20 min, 3 hr]

5. Profile ascent from low level at A (i.e. minimum safe altitude) towards B until nephelometer suggests you are well above aerosol layers (anticipated FL100) at 500ft per minute below 3000ft and 1000ft/min above 3000ft (travelling 80km in this time). Continue to point B at high level if necessary, with SWS and SHIMS pointing upwards.
[10 min, T=3hr 10 min]
 6. At point B perform FAAM outside turn to re-orient on a reciprocal heading.
[5 mins, T=3hr 15 min]
 7. Set of 2 orbits above point B
[10 mins, T=3hr 25 min]
 8. SLR of 15 minutes at FL100 (or above aerosol) back towards A. SWS and SHIMS to point downwards during this time.
[15 mins, T=3hr 40 min]
 9. Broken profile descent in region of point A until within aerosol layer
[10 mins, T=3hr 50 min]
 10. FAAM outside turn onto heading towards B
[5 mins, T=3hr 50 min]
 11. Perform a SLR from A to B within the aerosol layer for in-situ sampling.
[15 mins, T=4hr 05 min]
 12. FAAM turn and broken profile descent to low level (100ft) over point B.
[5 mins, T= 4hr 10 min]
 13. Set of 2 orbits above point B
[10 mins, T= 4hr 20 min]
 14. 15 min SLR at low level (100ft) towards point A with SWS and SHIMS pointing upwards for first 10 minutes and downwards for final 5 minutes (to get sea state and albedo)
[15 mins, T= 4hr 35 min]
- Alternatively: If cloud present aloft perform AMPEP run from Waypoint 40 to 45 at 2000' in aerosol layer and return in sawtooth pattern from MSA to 1000' below airway minimum.
15. Arrive point A at low level, recover to Rotterdam for refuel
[30 min, T=5 hr 5 mins]

Other comments:

Power on at 0700 local

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B362

6th May 2008

Summary of the weather conditions:

Atlantic low positioned west of Iceland (978 mbar) and High over Denmark, extending North-South from Norway and into Germany. A cold front associated with the low will extend N-S across the Irish Sea to Biscay, held stationary by high.

Anticyclonic flow from Central Europe expected to enter southern North Sea during the day.

Points defined:

A9-A8-A7/E7-E6-E5-E4-E3-E2-E1/F3-F2 then

Summary of the flight:

A successful pair of flights (B362 and B363) were carried out on the first day of science during the EUCAARI detachment to Oberpfaffenhofen. The conditions were generally clear skies though with some Cu over land areas, especially the higher terrain of the Black Forest and Taunus mountains, and the Dutch coast. A low level science leg was conducted from Oberpfaffenhofen to the west and then heading north over the Black Forest and up the Rhine Valley. Concentrations of aerosol particles were generally low at the south end of this run but increased as the aircraft continued northward. At the south end of the Rhine Valley the scattering coefficient measurements (blue) were of the order of $30\text{-}50 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$. Arriving at E6, CO steadily increased from 250 ppb to 300 ppb but was very variable when crossing the plumes. On this leg the AMS measured $6 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ of organic particulate; $9 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ of nitrate and $6 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ of sulphate. The CCN showed a high activated fraction. The wet nephelometer was not seeing much growth, a potentially anomalous result.

As point E5 was reached the σ_{blue} increased to 100 Mm^{-1} and CO was 260 ppb. At this point the wet nephelometer was seeing an $f(90)$ of around 1.6 which appeared more consistent with the other data. North of Frankfurt the pollution reduced over higher terrain, this cleaner air was observed between E5 and E3. The pollution increased over the flood plain of the Rhine (E2) with a very large CO plume of 500 ppb on a higher regional background of 300 ppb closer to the coast. A filter was exposed in this region. Over the Netherlands, σ_{blue} was larger than 150 Mm^{-1} and CO was above 300 ppb. Several major sources of industry were passed on the way to the coast, including major refineries. Off the mouth of the Rhine, many ships were anchored waiting to enter the coastal ports. Significant emissions may be expected in this region. Two points A and B were defined off the Norfolk and Suffolk coast of England between two upper level airways away from any contrails. The sky was clear in this region. MODIS images clearly showed the pollution load across the North Sea in this region. The radiation flight plan was followed as in the Mission Science Brief though with 12 minutes SLR not 15 minutes. A profile from A to B was conducted that ended at FL100 from 50'. This showed the pollution layer extending to FL060 with a peak σ_{blue} of 70 Mm^{-1} at about 2700 ft. This layer appeared to be the regional transport from continental Europe. A second pollution layer was observed from the surface to about 1000 ft which increased to a surface maximum σ_{blue} of close to 200 Mm^{-1} . The total optical depth was approximately 0.075 as estimated from this profile, though not all of the column would have been observed by the low level orbits which were conducted at 500'. The high level run at FL100 from B to A was conducted from B to A and the orbits were conducted at point A (a change from the flight plan). A broken descent at A was conducted to 2500' at the peak of the aerosol layer then a filter was taken during the SLR. The final low level run from B to A was conducted before the orbits. The radiation measurements were all conducted in clear skies and appeared to be very successful. The aircraft did not conduct science in transit to Rotterdam. No pirouette BBR calibrations were possible on landing at Rotterdam due to cloud.

Hugh Coe 7/5/08

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.362** Date 6/5/2008 Name HUGH COE Page 1 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0910Z	3/0	4900'	270	47°54'N 8°48'E	Heading to A8
0936Z	R1	4830'			Then to A7/E7.
					$\sigma_{\text{sea}} \sim 50 \text{ Mn}^{-1}$ near Munich but falling to 35 Mn^{-1} .
0942Z	P2	4830' to 2700'			net neph seeing near the dry so operator rebooting.
0945:57	end P2 start R2	2700'			End P2 at A7.
					Starting run up Rhine Valley North towards Netherlands
					CO rose a little to 270 ppb; O_3 dropped. Some neph variation though remain $30-50 \text{ Mn}^{-1}$.
0958					Arriving turning point E6 Pollution steadily increasing CO from 250 to close to 300 ppb but very variable when crossing plumes. Neph also varies $\sigma_{\text{base}} \sim 75 \text{ Mn}^{-1}$ but v variable - all small aerosol particles
					Clear skies v few small Ca puncturing BL top but largely clear.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B³⁶²** Date **6/5/08** Name **HUGH COE** Page **2** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ org } 9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ nitrate } AMS 6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ sulfate }
					can high activated fraction not neph not seeing much growth though (doesn't seem correct)
10:03	end R2 P3	2700 → 3800'			
10:05:35	add P3 start R3	3600'			Some Cu above us but close to up to 3900'
10:08:33	R3.	3200'			recommence, some height change to avoid air traffic but this means we are dipping the top of the BL.
10:10					A fair amount of Cu over terrain for last 10 mins Away from terrain Cu much less.
10:15:11	R3 cont.	3300'			Now v close to cloudbase of new small Cu. neph $\sigma_{\text{base}} \approx 90-100 \text{ m}^{-1}$ new CO $\approx 26 \text{ ppb}$ Let neph now seems to be better seeing growth of 16 at RH of 90%. (Frank/Jet)
10:17:45	R3 cont.	3380'			Point ES readout

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....³⁶² Date 4/5/08 Name MUSKOC Page 3.... of7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:20:07	23 ^{R23}	3400'			neph shows pollution much less here
10:21	R23	adjust to 3200' due to change in OAH			SSM _w and CO ~240ppb
10:26:33	R23	3200'			Start arrive E1 turning point
					Over higher ground here and more polluted.
10:36:21	R23	3200'			TURNING POINT E3.
					There is much less aerosol in BL's region.
10:38:32	end R23 start P5	3200' → 2300'			
10:40:33	end P5 start R4	2300'			Passing a major cooling tower to immediate left
10:42		2300'			Starting filters.
					Neph and CO has increased as we filter into BL.
10:48		2400'			Position E2
					CO now 330ppb high since last descent and start of Mission
					$\sigma_{\text{blue}} \approx 100 \text{ M}^{-1}$.
10:52		2400'			Brief CO pulse to 500ppb
10:57:25					nothing in neph.
10:57:28					E1 reached
10:58:30					filters closed.
11:05:48					D1 reached
11:17					heading to J2.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B362** Date 6/5/08 Name MUGH COE Page 4 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Lighter cloud now but present over Netherlands
					CO ~ 250 ppb
					neph $\sigma_{blue} \sim 100 M^{-1}$ $\sigma_{red} \sim 47 M^{-1}$
11:12:30					Passing major industry & cooling towers on LHS
11:16:08	R4	2800 ft			Vis now decreasing neph $\sigma_{blue} 120 M^{-1}$ $\sigma_{red} 36 M^{-1}$ CO 280 ppb
11:17:17					JZ reached heading 50 MVA.
11:22					Crossing Dutch coast at the mouth of the Rhine & refineries now to north and east
11:23					- Aerosol scattering now inc significantly $\sigma_{blue} \sim 150 M^{-1}$
11:25					Many ships offshore waiting to go into Rhine and Rotterdam may be some ship emissions little cloud cover aloft at all
					Defined a rally point A and secondary B off the Norfolk and Suffolk coast.

40 M_n^{-1} 4×10^{-5}
 3000 ft
 1000 ~
 > 0.04A00

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.362** Date 6/5/08 Name HUGH COE Page 5 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:36:28					Neph she is doc in scattering since leaving Dutch coast σ_{blue} 30 M_n^{-1} - 50 M_n^{-1} and σ_{red} 15 M_n^{-1} - 25 M_n^{-1} . beginning to rise CO lower 240ppb than before vis shears now pollutive to north as forecast
11:45:54	end of R4 P6	2400' → 1500'			avoidance of helicopter traffic and positioning for work between points A and B.
11:47:30	end P6 stat R5	1500'			
11:51:07	end R5	1500'			Turning and descent to point A. to 50'
11:52:48	stat P7	1500' to 50'			down to pt A for profile to B
11:55:15	end P7 stat P8	50' → FL100			A heading S to B.
12:07:50	end P8	FL100			SCOS and SHIMS now pointing down
12:11:11	stat R6	FL100			B → A at FL100.
12:11:11					45° orbits x 2.
12:22:24	end of run 6 stat R6 and orb 1	FL100			stat orbit over point A.
12:24:07	and orb 1				
12:24:12	stat orb 2				very good orbits - clear overhead
12:26:08	end orbit 2				
12:27:28	P9 Stat R7	FL100 → FL080			Breaker profile descent over point A.
12:29:48		F080			Break in P9. at FL080

Mission Scientist's Log

6/5/08

Flight No **B362** Date **6/5/08** Name **M COE** Page **6** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:35:50	rd P 9 Run 7	2500'			Point A in coastal layer heading towards B σ_{blue} 75 Mn^{-1} red σ_{red} 31 Mn^{-1} SLWS to point downward for 3 mins and upward until end of run (9 minutes). then in correct position for abuts
12:48:58	END R7 Start P10	2500' → 100'			Profile descent to 100' at B, cleaner at this end.
12:51:17	END R7 Intermittent	1000'			at intermittent to low
12:53:09	P10	1000' → 50'			recommencing at Sea state calm.
12:56:58	end P10 Start R8	80' → 100'			very pronounced lower aerosol layer 200 Mn^{-1}
13:00:00					SLWS needs switching up for down.
		upper layers polluted but less so and suspect this is the real European outflow			
		lower v polluted likely Dutch coastal pollution maybe more fresh			

Mission Scientist's LogFlight No **B.362** Date 6 May 2008 Name Megan Northey Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:05Z					T/O - 9:05Z Oberpfaffenhofen
9:18	P1	6.8kft			
9:20	R1	4.8kft			
9:21	P2	4.7kft			
9:22	R1	4.5kft			
					Co peak to \approx 300
					passing A7 at / meet alt pt.
0944	R2	2700			and now heading north
09:58:19		2.4kft			A7 E6 turning pt
10:03					terrain coming up below us
	P3				profile climb to 3800 ft
					going through ^{by} some light cloud
10:05:55	R3	3600			Start of run
					going up to 3900 - too close to traffic
10:07					back to 3900 - lots of traffic around
10:08:33	R3	3200ft			reconnect my run
	"	"			Nephelometer climbed to \approx 100 m ⁻¹
	"	"			AMS seeing several $\mu\text{s}/\text{m}^3$
10:17:40	"	"			passing E5
10:22	"	"			easing left b/c of traffic
					levels of pollution low again
					-Neph blue - 60 m ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...362** Date **6 May 2008** Name **Megan Nothman** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~10:30	R3	3200			passing E4
10:34		"			passing E2
10:34					Contrails above
10:38					passing huge power plant
10:39	R3	"			filters starting
10:43	"				NO ₂ taking off
10:46					just at Netherlands border
10:50	"				plume - CO up to 500 ppb
~10:52					passing E1
11:05:49					passing D1
11:08:00	"	"			another plume
11:10:00					passing another plant
11:14					turning towards SOMVA (J2) ↳ UK airspace
11:18	"	"			refineries on right of aircraft
11:20					almost to coast - plume picking up blue sect = 150 m-1
11:22	"	"			took photo of Dutch coast
11:24					shallow water - several wave lines plume clear skies + a
11:26	"	"			few contrails above - not bad for radiation work
					- Hugh has mapped out a 12min run for SLRS / radiation work.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....³⁶² Date 6 May 2008 Name Megan Northrup Page 3 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~11:24	R3	3200			over N. sea - low concentrations now - blue scat < 50m-1
11:37	R3	3200			plan is to work up + down 20 line for points "A" + "B" for radiator work
11:45:56	P6	3200- 1500			profile to 1500ft at 40 very nice + clear above - no clouds
11:47:32	R5	1500			short run at 1500ft
11:48*					contrail above, falcon sighted
11:51:09	end of R5				turning towards pt 40 - big Chem planes no aerosol
11:52:48	P7	1500- 50			at 40 increase in aerosol, chem starting at 500 ft
11:55					peak around 200 ft
11:55:15	P8	50- 10,000ft			full profile up
(end) 12:22:28	R6	10000ft			Run at 10,000
12:22:37		10000 ft			2x orbits at 45°
12:27:29	P9	10000 - 7000			descent to 8000 ft
12:29:49					interrupt contrail above possibly
12:35:52	R7	2.2kt			run through aerosol A → B
12:35	R7	2.2kt			
12: ⁴⁸ 35					large plume in aerosol at 12: 35 ⁴⁸

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 06 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
		08:45 2dc running 2dp running pcasp running vref 8.55v flow 0.7 sid 1 recording b362-1.srd ffssp recording on, base values stable vref 3.7v ffssp computer cannot see Horace – network problem															
091000																T/0	
091800	300	0.1	2	1		0	0	0	0							P1 start	
092047	630	0.1	3	5		0	0	0	0							P1 end r1.1 start 5100ft	
092203	550	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0							4800 ft adjust	
092500	630	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0								
093000	540	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0							Brief capture on 2dc	
093500	520	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0							Alpha 8 turning point	
094000	540	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0								
094200																Pcasp heater on	
094500	800	0.1	4	3		0	0	0	0								
094600																Start run 2	
095000	680	0.1	4	3		0	0	0	0								
095500	650	0.1	4	3		0	0	0	0								
100000	760	0.1	4	3		0	0	0	0								
100500	750	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0								
101000	1000	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0								
101330																2dp logging frequency reduced	
101500	1000	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0								
102000	720	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0								
102500	900	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0								
103000	900	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0								
103500	750	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0								
104000	1300	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0								
104500	1300	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0								
105000	1000	0.1	7	3		0	0	0	0								
105500	1400	0.1	7	3		0	0	0	0								
110000	1000	0.1	7	3		0	0	0	0								
110500	1014	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
111000	1200	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
111500	1200	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 06 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
112000	1500	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
112500	1800	0.1	9	3		0	0	0	0								
113000	1020	0.1	9	3		0	0	0	0								
113500	750	0.1	9	3		0	0	0	0								
114000	750	0.1	9	3		0	0	0	0								
114500	680	0.1	10	3		0	0	0	0								
115000	760	0.1	10	3		0	0	0	0								
115500	3500	0.01	10	10		0	0	0	0							50ft	
120000	300	0.1	10	1		0	0	0	0								
120500	60	0.1	10	0		0	0	0	0								
121000	50	0.1	10	0		0	0	0	0								
121500	80	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
122000	75	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
123000	64	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
123200	60	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
123400	650	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
123600	1275	0.1	11	0		0	0	0	0								
123800	961	0.1	11	3		0	0	0	0								
124100	890	0.1	11	3		0	0	0	0								
124500	780	0.1	11	3		0	0	0	0								
125000	750	0.1	12	3		0	0	0	0								
125700	3000	0.1	12	10		0	0	0	0								
130000	2600	0.1	12	10		0	0	0	0								
130200	2640	0.1	13	10		0	0	0	0								
130400	2580	0.1	13	10		0	0	0	0								
130600	2400	0.1	13	10		0	0	0	0								
130800	2640	0.1	13	10		0	0	0	0								
131000	2580	0.1	13	3		0	0	0	0								
133630																End of science	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B362 **T/O:** 091226
Date of flight: 6/05/2008 **Land:** 135141

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = Blocks written = Bad reads =
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 0 End = 24000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images All images are noise, further processing not done Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B****Date of Flight:**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.7 0 240000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B362_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

06:58:57.14 --- - - - -
06:58:57.15 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:58:57.15 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:58:57.15 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B362
06:58:57.16 --- - - - -
06:59:43.90 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:59:50.51 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
06:59:51.06 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
06:59:56.33 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
06:59:57.99 SWS 170.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:00:16.10 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
07:00:35.13 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:01:24.15 SWS 102.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:01:41.85 --- - - - -
07:01:41.85 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:01:41.85 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:01:41.85 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B362
07:01:41.85 --- - - - -
07:01:46.95 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:01:50.71 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:01:59.83 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
07:02:01.50 SWS 169.2 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:02:27.69 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
07:02:28.80 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:02:43.41 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:02:43.50 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:02:43.59 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:03:08.76 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:03:10.30 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:03:11.88 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:03:14.08 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:14.08 LSH - - 600 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:17.89 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:17.90 USH - - 600 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:20.79 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:20.79 SWS - - 600 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
07:03:22.44 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:03:23.73 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
07:03:24.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:03:25.27 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
07:03:26.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:03:37.07 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 50ms.
07:03:37.08 USH - - 50 50 NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 50ms.
07:03:40.05 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:03:40.05 USH - - 100 100 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
07:03:43.85 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
07:03:43.86 USH - - 300 300 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
07:03:48.46 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 300ms.
07:03:48.47 SWS - - 300 300 NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 300ms.
07:03:52.84 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
07:03:52.84 SWS - - 200 200 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
07:03:56.09 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:03:58.35 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:04:01.18 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:04:13.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:14.25 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:04:15.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:16.04 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:04:17.60 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:18.03 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:04:18.96 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:19.88 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:20.06 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:23.64 SWS - - - - Idling
07:04:23.68 USH - - - - Idling

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07:04:23.81 LSH - - - - Idling
07:04:29.16 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:04:34.39 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:34.39 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:34.40 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:04:36.82 SWS - - - - Idling
07:04:38.22 USH - - - - Idling
07:04:41.03 LSH - - - - Idling
07:04:46.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:46.31 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:46.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:04:52.93 SWS - - - - Idling
07:04:52.95 LSH - - - - Idling
07:04:52.97 USH - - - - Idling
08:25:44.92 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:25:44.93 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:25:44.93 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:25:53.78 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:26:01.49 USH - - - - Idling
08:26:01.53 LSH - - - - Idling
08:26:01.69 SWS - - - - Idling
08:26:06.20 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:26:10.75 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:10.75 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:10.76 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:14.75 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:26:14.89 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:26:14.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:26:17.21 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:18.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:21.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:58.24 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:04.71 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:11.19 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:14.76 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:22.52 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:25.44 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:47.12 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:27:53.26 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:07.84 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:26.59 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:31.46 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:41.16 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:44.73 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:54.76 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:29:05.44 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:29:16.44 USH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:29:25.49 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:29:25.50 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:29:30.04 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
08:29:30.05 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
08:29:38.40 USH - - - - Idling
08:29:38.42 SWS - - - - Idling
08:29:38.86 LSH - - - - Idling
08:30:58.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:58.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:58.17 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:13.95 LSH - - - - Idling
08:31:14.00 USH - - - - Idling
08:31:14.04 SWS - - - - Idling
08:46:36.73 --- - - - -
08:46:36.73 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:46:36.73 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:46:36.73 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B362
08:46:36.73 --- - - - -
08:46:41.63 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
08:46:43.15 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
08:46:45.47 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED

```

```

08:51:11.74 --- - - - -
08:51:11.75 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:51:11.75 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:51:11.75 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B362
08:51:11.75 --- - - - -
08:51:16.47 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:51:17.29 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:51:32.78 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:51:47.82 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:51:49.88 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:51:51.28 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:51:53.14 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:51:55.76 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:51:57.74 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:51:59.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:51:59.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:51:59.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:04.09 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:52:04.09 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:52:07.67 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:52:07.67 USH - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 200ms.
08:52:11.35 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:52:11.36 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:52:13.85 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
08:52:13.85 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
08:52:17.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:17.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:17.71 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:18.09 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:18.49 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:18.69 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:20.11 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:20.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:24.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:27.20 SWS - - - - Idling
08:52:27.27 USH - - - - Idling
08:52:27.63 LSH - - - - Idling
08:52:29.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:29.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:29.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:30.36 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:30.77 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:30.97 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:52:32.39 SWS - - - - Idling
08:52:32.79 USH - - - - Idling
08:52:33.88 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:52:36.58 LSH - - - - Idling
08:52:39.45 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:52:46.33 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:46.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:46.35 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:48.80 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:52:53.45 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:52:55.89 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:52:58.09 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:53:00.54 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:01.07 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:53:07.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:53:07.77 USH - - - - Idling
08:53:07.88 SWS - - - - Idling
08:53:08.34 LSH - - - - Idling
08:23:45.49 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:23:52.51 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:24:06.94 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:24:18.38 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
08:24:19.49 SWS 90.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
08:24:45.68 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:25:01.49 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.

```

08:25:05.21	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
08:25:06.32	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:01:25.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:25.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:25.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:21.38	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:02:21.39	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:02:26.13	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:02:26.13	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:02:30.03	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
09:02:30.03	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
09:02:37.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:37.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:37.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:37.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:02:37.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:02:38.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:39.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:40.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:41.18	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:02:46.32	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:02:49.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:51.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:53.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:53.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:53.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:02:55.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:55.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:02:56.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:07:54.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler temp at 3 deg
09:13:05.73	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:13:05.74	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
09:13:12.65	LSH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
09:13:12.66	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
09:13:19.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:13:25.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:14:10.67	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:14:10.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:14:11.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:18:05.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
09:20:26.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5700 ft
09:21:18.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:21:18.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:21:18.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:21:20.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:20.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:21:25.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:22:36.25	---	-	-	-	-	***
09:25:39.01	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:25:40.73	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:25:50.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:25:50.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:25:50.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:25:51.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:25:52.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:25:57.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:41:52.98	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:41:53.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:41:54.65	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:45:54.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:46:18.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 2 2700
09:46:58.11	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:46:59.80	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:54:11.58	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
09:54:13.29	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:55:55.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:55.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:56.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:57.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

09:55:57.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:02.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:50.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 2 deg
09:58:44.59	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:58:46.28	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:01:33.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:33.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:33.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:35.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:35.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:40.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:53.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
10:10:08.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler 6 deg
10:18:10.74	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:18:11.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:18:12.46	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:18:18.70	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:18:18.70	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:18:25.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:25.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:25.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:26.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:26.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:30.52	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:18:30.52	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:18:32.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:32.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:32.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:33.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:34.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:34.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:35.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:18:39.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:42.47	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:18:42.48	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:18:44.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:44.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:44.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:45.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:45.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:51.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:20.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:19:30.86	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:19:30.86	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:19:33.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:33.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:33.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:34.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:34.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:40.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:42.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 5 deg
10:22:48.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 4 deg
10:30:27.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 3 deg
10:32:39.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 2
10:37:21.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
10:38:51.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 5
10:40:35.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4 at 2300 ft
10:41:48.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:41:50.56	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:42:08.63	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
10:42:08.64	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
10:42:11.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:11.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:12.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:13.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:13.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:18.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:08.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
10:47:00.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** moving sws

10:47:07.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:08.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:26.75	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
10:47:27.91	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:47:52.58	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
10:47:52.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:48:11.61	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 60.000
10:48:34.99	SWS	60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:48:36.15	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:48:39.90	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 179.500
10:48:48.19	SWS	179.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
10:49:04.92	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 160.000
10:49:23.48	SWS	160.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 25.000
10:49:24.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:49:25.23	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:49:35.83	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 10.000
10:49:46.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:49:58.20	SWS	10.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
10:49:58.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:50:06.52	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 45.000
10:50:14.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:50:22.72	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 20.000
10:50:28.17	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:50:37.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:39.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:42.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:50:52.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** finnished moving sws around
10:51:00.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:51:23.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
10:51:34.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:51:43.58	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 35ms.
10:51:43.58	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 35ms.
10:51:46.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:46.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:50.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:50.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:50.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:51.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:51.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:56.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:15.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
10:59:17.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:01:31.08	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:01:31.09	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:01:36.41	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 50ms.
11:01:36.42	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 50ms.
11:01:38.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:38.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:38.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:39.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:40.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:40.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:45.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:51.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:01:56.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:59.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:59.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:59.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:01.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:01.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:06.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:17.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:07:29.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:07:31.14	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:07:40.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:40.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:40.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:41.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:41.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:07:46.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:06.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
11:09:52.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:09:57.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:11:49.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
11:12:23.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:20:44.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
11:24:12.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
11:24:39.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:39.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:39.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:42.35	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:24:44.09	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:24:46.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:46.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:46.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:48.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:48.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:48.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:49.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:49.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:55.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:46.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:30:30.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** check of int time for orbits (moving telescope)
11:30:32.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:30:33.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:43.16	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 30.000
11:30:53.71	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 40.000
11:31:03.24	SWS	40.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 170.000
11:31:04.97	SWS	170.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:31:15.10	SWS	170.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
11:31:16.25	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:31:25.81	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 35.000
11:31:26.96	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:31:40.43	SWS	35.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:31:43.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:44.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:49.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** finished
11:31:53.62	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:31:57.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:57.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:57.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:58.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:58.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:02.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:02.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:03.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:03.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:03.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:35.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 3 deg
11:35:02.11	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:35:03.85	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:35:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:15.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:16.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:16.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:17.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:21.29	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
11:35:21.29	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
11:35:23.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:25.47	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:35:25.48	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:35:27.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:27.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:27.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:28.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:28.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:34.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:37:05.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
11:37:22.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:38:16.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
11:39:53.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** 5 deg
11:40:17.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
11:46:03.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile descent
11:47:33.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at 1500 ft
11:47:53.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:48:49.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
11:50:52.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:51:15.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
11:52:39.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:39.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:39.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:41.34	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:52:43.04	SWS	-3.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:52:44.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:44.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:44.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:48.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:48.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:48.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:48.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:49.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:50.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:55.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:16.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:20.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:20.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:21.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:21.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:21.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:22.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:28.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:23.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
11:57:19.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
11:58:06.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
12:07:08.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** f1 100
12:07:30.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:30.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:30.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:32.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:07:34.23	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:07:35.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:35.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:35.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:39.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:39.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:39.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:41.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:41.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:46.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:14.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
12:19:17.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:17.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:17.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:18.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:19.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:24.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:23.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:24.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:24.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:30.98	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
12:20:32.73	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:20:33.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:33.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:33.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:39.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit

12:20:44.48	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 15ms.
12:20:44.49	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 15ms.
12:20:50.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:51.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:51.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:51.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:52.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:57.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:26.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 1 at 45 deg to the right
12:23:16.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
12:24:09.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** end
12:24:15.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 2
12:24:18.47	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 30ms.
12:24:18.48	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 15ms to 30ms.
12:24:21.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:21.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:21.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:21.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:22.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:28.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:30.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit
12:26:09.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:26:11.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 2 at 45 deg
12:26:24.22	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
12:26:24.23	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
12:26:26.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:26.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:26.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:27.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:27.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:32.12	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:26:33.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:33.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:26:35.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:35.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:35.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:26:36.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:37.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:26:42.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:31.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile decest
12:29:45.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
12:29:50.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** interupt p 9
12:31:34.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** p9
12:36:14.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 7 2500 ft
12:38:42.64	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:38:44.35	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:38:47.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:47.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:47.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:48.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:48.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:53.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:58.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:58.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:39:59.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:40:00.97	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:40:02.72	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:40:05.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:05.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:05.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:07.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:07.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:07.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:08.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:08.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:14.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:45.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 10
12:56:55.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:55.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:56:55.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:57.84	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:56:59.58	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:57:01.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:01.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:01.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:04.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:04.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:04.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:05.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:05.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:06.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:09.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:11.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:07.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:58:07.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:58:07.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:58:09.49	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:58:11.28	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:58:12.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:12.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:12.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:02.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:02.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:03.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:04.65	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:59:06.37	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:59:07.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:07.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:07.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:35.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:35.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:35.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:36.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:36.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:42.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:39.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
13:07:47.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:07:47.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:07:47.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:07:48.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:48.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:50.37	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:07:54.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:00.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:00.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:00.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:01.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:01.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:07.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:21.77	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
13:08:21.78	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
13:08:25.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:25.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:25.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:26.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:26.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:26.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:33.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:56.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 3 turn to right BA 45 deg, sza 39.17
13:11:25.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 3
13:11:43.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of orbit 4 turn to right ba
13:11:54.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:12:36.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit 4
13:12:36.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:08.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:13:33.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science
13:13:37.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:37.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

13:14:00.26	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
13:14:00.27	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
13:14:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:04.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:04.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:05.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:05.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:11.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:39.44	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
13:18:40.61	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:18:54.47	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 130.000
13:19:00.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No. **B.362**.....

 Date **6/5/08**.....

 Operator's name: **J. Bowers**.....

 Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
092047	1	5000	16					
	?	4800	16.3	20.7	46	↑40	15	
0932	"	"	16.9	24	65	↓25	39	CANT GET RH PAST ≈ 65% - DROPPING DOWN TO SER + CHANGE
				25	44	↑40	25	- RH DID DROP SO HUMIDIFIER WORKING
0938		2						CITICOR LOCKED UP! ON/OFF
0946	2	2700				↑48		NOT SEEING MUCH EFFECT BELOW 90% - SUB ZERO READINGS
0950								PROG STOP - TEST WET NEFF ZERO
0955	2							WET ZERO - OK ON NEFF MAIN
	2	↓	18.2	38	55	↑40	25	PROG RESTART + TEMP UP
10:04:47	R3	↑3800		36	43	↓19	49	- SEE SOME
10:04:47	R3	↑3800						
10:05:55	R3	3600						
10:08:38	R3	3200		42	54	↑48		
10:13	"	"		43	92	↓19	49	NOW SEEING GROWTH ≈ 1.6 @ 90%
10:19	"	"		40	56	↑39		PLUS INC TO 49°C
10:25	"	"	17.8	40.6	93	↓19		≈ 1.6 @ 90%
10:30	"	"		42	61	↑39		
10:35				39	90	↓19		≈ 1.8 @ 90%

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.362**.....

 Date **6/5/08**.....

 Operator's name: **S. Bowles**.....

 Page **2** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:50	4		18	41	88	↓19		≈ 1.7 @ 88%
10:56	"			41	56.8	↑31		(DOING FILTERS - DELAY IN HUMIDGRAM.)
11:04			18	41	75%	↑49		←
11:06			18	41	85%	↓19		≈ 1.8 @ 89%
11:11			18	43	58%	↑49		←
11:17			18	42	87%	↓15		≈ 1.5 @ 87%
11:23			18.2	41	53%	↑45		
11:27			18.1	39	86%	↓15		≈ 1.5 > 1.6 @ 86%
11:34			18.1	37.6	48%	↑45		
11:39			18.2	38.6	86%	↓15		≈ 1.5 @ 86%
11:45:56	P6 ↓	T ^o 1500	18.3	36.5	50%	↑45		
47:32	R5	1500						
11:52	P7 ↓	1500 ↓ 50						LEAVE @ 85%
11:55	P8 ↑	50 → 10,000						" " " UNTIL 5000ft
12:04	P8	7000						PUMP ^{CHILLER} OFF - TO HSH.
12:29	↓		14.9	0.8	34%			PUMP (CHILLER) ON @ 3000ft
12:39:35	P9 ↓		15.0	1.5	32%	↑45		
12:40:00	R.	2100	17.9	37%	37%	↓15		≈ 1.4 @ 87%
12:45:	R	"	18	38%	55%	↑45		
49:46	P10	↓ 1000ft						LEAVE @ 26%

Flight:

B362

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:	
Heimann:	
Deiced Temp:	
Non-deiced Temp:	

Hygrometers

FWVS:	
Buck CR2:	
General Eastern:	
Johnson Williams:	
Nevzorov:	
Total Water Probe:	

Cameras

Downward Facing:	
Forward Facing:	
Rearward Facing:	
Upward Facing:	

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:	
GIN Applanix:	
INU Honeywell:	
Radar Altimeter:	
RVSM IAS:	
RVSM Static Pressure:	
XR5 GPS:	

Misc Core

AMTG:	
AVAPS:	
Cabin Pressure:	
Fax machine:	
Printer:	
S9 Static Pressure:	
Satcom C:	
Satcom H:	
Turb Centre-Static:	
Turb Left Right:	
Turb Up-Down:	
Turb Horizontal Chk:	
Turb Vertical Chk:	
Weather Radar:	
DLUs:	
DLU AERACK:	
DLU BBR Lower:	
DLU BBR Upper:	
DLU Core Chem:	
DLU Core Consoles:	
DLU Port Aft:	
DLU Port Fwd:	
DLU Stbd Fwd:	

Radiometers

Lower:	
BBR (clear) Lower:	
BBR (IR) Lower:	
BBR (red) Lower:	
Upper:	
BBR (clear) Upper:	
BBR (IR) Upper:	
BBR (red) Upper:	
ARIES:	
DEIMOS:	
IR Camera:	
JNO2 Lower:	
JNO2 Upper:	
JO1D Lower:	
JO1D Upper:	
MARSS:	
SHIMS Lower:	
SHIMS Upper:	
SWS:	
TAFTS:	

Cloud Probes

2DC:	
2DP:	
FFSSP:	
PCASP:	
2DS:	
ADA:	
CAPS:	
CCN:	
CDP:	
CIP 100:	
CIP 25:	
CPI:	
CVI:	
SID1:	
SID2:	

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:	
CPC 3786 H2O:	
Filters 47mm:	
Filters 90mm:	
Neph - Dry:	
Neph - Wet:	
PSAP:	
AMS:	
CPC 3025 (AMS):	
INC:	
VACC:	
CPC 3010A (CVI):	
SP2:	
UHSAS:	

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:	
NOx TE42C:	
Ozone TE49C:	
Ozone TE49:	
SO2 TE43C:	
TDLAS (NIR) CH4:	
TDLAS (NIR) CO2:	
FAGE:	
Formaldehyde:	
NOx FAAM:	
NOxy:	
ORAC:	
PAN:	
PERCA:	
Peroxide:	
PTRMS:	
TDLAS (1C):	
WAS Bags:	
WAS Bottles:	
Misc Non-Core	
CASI/ATM:	
LIDAR:	
LTI:	
SAW Hygrometer:	

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B362

Date: 06 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not responding to serial commands. Changed Terminal server (HORNET) for HOUSEFLY. Satcom channel working okay and CVI?
2. HORACE Display – All INU paras reading 0 . Changed track-plot default to GIN paras and lat, long on the header window to GIN.
3. FFC – smudges on camera window appeared in flight, probably insects – inform Avalon post-flight
4. CGPS – new software installed but CGPS still doesn't work.

Instrument Status roundup

NephS – Wet Neph pc rebooted after about 1 hour into flight, then okay.

AMS – fine , SMPS intermittent

CCN – all fine apart from pressure

PAN/WAS/Core Chem – no was, pan problem with valve, core chem. okay new revised regime for CO cals, tdlas as normal

SWS – fine

Cloud Physics – 2Dc fine 2DP noisy, PCASP fine sid 1 & ffssp fine

CAPS/SP2/CPI – CPI not run, SP2 and CAPS okay.

Aircraft

1. Smell of “hot rubber” in first hour of flight. Nothing found

ISDN Emails

1 connection at 1108Z for about a minute to check for new emails – none received.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B362:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
2D-S / CAPS / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log was taken for this flight

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	12 Jun 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b362_090501_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b362_100501_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b362_110501_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b362_120501_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b362_130501_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b362_090455_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b362_100455_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b362_110455_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b362_120455_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b362_130455_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b362_090453_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b362_100453_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b362_110453_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b362_120453_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b362_130453_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b362_090458_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b362_100458_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b362_110458_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b362_120458_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b362_130458_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Hugh Coe

School of Earth, Atmospheric & Environmental Sciences
The University of Manchester
Simon Building
Oxford Road
Manchester
M13 9PL

Tel: +44 (0) 161 306 3935

Fax: +44 (0) 161 306 3951

if dialling from a Manchester University extension please use (77)63935

E-mail: hugh.coe@manchester.ac.uk

Flight B362 12:12:20

Heading 0 deg Speed 247 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb

Lat 52°12.0'N Long 1°54.0'E Wind 127 ms/1/360 deg

Temp -1.3C Dewpoint -30.79C

From 11:50:54 to now

Current values

++++ STATIC PRESSURE
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP
++++ DEW POINT

696.48 mb
-1.31 deg C
-30.8 deg C